

Quantum Mechanics and Writing the LHS of $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ in terms of a Gradient? Part 2

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In Part 1, we tried to obtain free particle quantum mechanics by writing the LHS side of $dp/dt = F$ as a gradient because the RHS $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$ may be written in this manner for a conservative force. Here we argue that just as $V(x)$ has physical meaning, $p = \text{grad partial} (-Et+px)$ (found in (1)) should represent the physical potential created by a free particle. That does not change the fact that the particle center-of-mass moves as $x=vt$, but the interaction created by the particle should be described in terms of a potential and this was found to be $-Et+px$. From the point of view of a force system (e.g. a 2-slit system) interacting with the potential, one needs a potential created by the free particle. The potential $-Et+px$ shows that an interaction at t,x has the same potential value as one at $t+\hbar/E$ and $x+\hbar/p$. Given that this potential follows from $dp/dt=\text{Force}$, we suggest it should be taken seriously and that it indicates there is the possibility of interaction at two different x points x and $x+\hbar/p$ in a stochastic manner. In other words, a single free particle could interact with one slit or the other of a 2-slit system if the slit separation is about \hbar/p .

This still leaves two questions. First, is such a two fold interaction deterministic or probabilistic. We suggest probabilistic because there are ranges for x and t . Second, why does the usual Lagrangian method of finding a stationary solution from $d \int dt L(x, dx/dt, t) = 0$ (leading to $d/dt dL/dv \text{ partial} - dL/dx \text{ partial} = 0$) not show this range in Δx ? We suggest that writing $p = \text{grad partial} (-Et+px)$ (so the potential is Lorentz invariant) removes the dynamics of the particle from the interacting force system (2-slits). The 2-slit is interacting with a free particle potential (not with its dynamic motion. The two need not be the same.

We suggest that there are two theories for describing a particle interaction, the single particle potential theory and Lagrangian formalism. We thus suggest that they must be linked and try to show how they compare and how they differ in a systematic manner.

The Notion of a Free Particle Potential

Newton's second law $F = dp/dt$ shows how a force changes momentum, but we argued in Part 1 that momentum is almost like a force. This may be seen in two ways. First, a moving object (with momentum) may deliver an impulse to a target and so from the target's point of view, it is like a force. Secondly, a rest mass (inertia) is like a force because it requires a force to start it moving. A Lorentz boost then creates E and p . Thus, momentum is closely related to special relativity. In Part 1, we argued that one may write for a free particle:

$$p = \text{grad} (\text{partial}) (-Et+px) \quad ((1))$$

Here, we argue that just as $V(x)$ is a potential for $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$ for a conservative force,

$-Et+px$ ((2)) is a potential related to p .

It is the free particle potential that a force system (e.g. 2-slit mechanism) would see. This potential depends on both t and x (to be Lorentz invariant). One might argue that given that the center-of-mass moves as:

$$x=vt \quad ((3))$$

that one might consider a t value and a corresponding $x=vt$. That is fine, but one may note that the potential ((2)) has another t and x value which yields the same potential value:

$$t+h\bar{v}/E \quad \text{and} \quad x+h\bar{v}/p \quad ((4))$$

When thinking in terms of a potential, which delivers the force to the force system (2-slit mechanism), one may have two different x,t points yielding the same potential. We suggest that this means that the interaction caused by the free particle is not restricted to x,t and that given that t and x change (but not according to the trajectory ((3))), this means that one has fluctuations or probability with respect to the interaction. In other words, there is a stochastic interaction which may be described in terms of probabilities. A probability which naturally creates the intervals of ((4)), is Lorentz invariant and leads to two body elastic scattering with conserved momentum and energy for product probabilities is:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

One may view the interaction of a free particle from the point of view of its potential and not simply $V(x)$. This has important consequences because it means that the particle's potential is not restricted to a single point on $x=vt$. This is different from interaction at the center-of-mass point which exists in a Newtonian description. If, however, $h\bar{v}/E$ and $h\bar{v}/p$ are of the order (or less than) dt and dx , such that these are tiny compared to time and length scales in the system, then it as if the particle's potential only acts at one point $x \approx x+h\bar{v}/p$ and $t \approx t+h\bar{v}/E$.

If one introduces a potential for the particle, similar to $V(x)$, one might argue that there should be some kind of link with Lagrangian theory which describes motion based on a Lagrangian which contains $V(x)$.

Relationship with Lagrangian Theory

Lagrangian theory introduces a Lagrangian, usually:

$$L = \text{Kinetic energy} - V(x) \quad \text{nonrelativistic} \quad ((6))$$

And then creates a differential equation by finding a stationary solution of:

$$D \text{ Integral } L(x, dx/dt, t) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } d/dt \partial L/\partial v \text{ partial} - \partial L/\partial x \text{ partial} = 0 \quad ((8))$$

(One may also include constraints via Lagrange multipliers.)

For a free particle, the Lagrangian is:

$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ relativistic ((9a)) and $L = m/2 v^2$ ((9b)) nonrelativistic

In both case, setting $v=x/t$ yields:

$$L = -Et + px \quad ((9))$$

In the relativistic case $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, while in the nonrelativistic case: $E = .5 m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$.

Lagrangian theory yields:

$d/dt \partial L / \partial v = 0$ for a free particle so $dv/dt = 0$ both relativistically and non relativistically.

Furthermore, $L = .5 m_0 v^2$ and $L t = t \cdot .5 m_0 v^2$ ((10)), so it seems that a question is: Why should one write $v=x/t$ and treat x and t as independent variables in a free particle potential as done in the above section.

We note that in order to create a potential like $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$, one needs to use a grad partial and for p this yields $p = \text{grad } (px)$, but this is not Lorentz invariant and so we suggest grad partial $(-Et + px)$. Thus, t and x appear naturally and don't restrict $dx \rightarrow 0$ $dt \rightarrow 0$ as $v = dx/dt$ does. This seems to be the fundamental difference which must then be considered when dealing with interactions with $V(x)$ because they can no longer occur in $dx \rightarrow 0$.

Furthermore, we note that single particle potential theory and Lagrangian cannot be two separate independent theories, they must be compatible, or at least one must pinpoint where a difference arises.

Lagrangian theory predicts $dv/dt = 0$ or $v = \text{constant} = dx/dt \rightarrow x = vt$ (starting point $x=0, t=0$) ((10))

One may notice that in this theory, $v = dx/dt$ ((11)) which is in fact its formal definition. There is nothing wrong with the definition $v = dx/dt$, but in the Lagrangian formalism, this derivative is linked to an interaction with $V(x)$ (i.e. integration of parts is applied to $dL/dv dv$ to create $-d/dt \partial L / \partial v$ partial. The use of dx/dt implies that an interaction with $V(x)$ occurs within $dx \rightarrow 0$, and this contradicts single particle potential theory.

For a free particle with starting point $x=0, t=0$, $v=x/t$ as well, and one does not impose the constraint of $dx \rightarrow 0, dt \rightarrow 0$ as in $v = dx/dt$.

Given that the two theories (section 1, single particle potential) and Lagrangian must be compatible, we see that they are in fact compatible if v in Lagrangian is replaced with x/t and the

action $L \cdot t$ considered. It is good that compatibility may be obtained so easily, but the catch is that the potential theory introduces dx and dt uncertainties of

$$dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \hbar/E \quad ((11))$$

Thus, an interaction does not take place simply at x, t of $x=vt$, but there is stochastic potential and probability as described in Part 1.

We then ask: Why does not regular Lagrangian theory predict this. We suggest that the reason is that one considers $V(x)$ and $v=dx/dt$. The derivative means that $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$. In other words, in a tiny dx , the particle moves with constant v (while being accelerated) so that it moves with $v+dv$ in the next dx . This is compatible with the single particle potential theory if \hbar/p and \hbar/E are tiny values compared with tiny dx, dt in the system. Then one may in fact use $v = dx/dt$ and use integration by parts in $D \int dt L(x, dx/dt, t)$ i.e.

$$DL = \int dt \left(\frac{dL}{dx} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{dL}{dv} \frac{dv}{dt} + \frac{dL}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad ((12))$$

One applies integration by parts to $d \frac{dx}{dt}$ so that $\frac{dL}{dv} \frac{dv}{dt}$ becomes $-\frac{d}{dt} \frac{dL}{V}$ ((13))

As a result, this approach implies $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$ intervals associated with $V(x)$ interacting with a particle moving with v . The single particle potential picture shows that this cannot be the case if $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ are not less than or of the order of dx, dt (which are tiny in the system). In such a case, one has stochasticity and dx/dt does not describe the interaction correctly, i.e. $V(x)$ does not act within a dx .

Instead, one may use an average Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to show how the particle potentials for different p values interact with constant momentum situations because each has its own $dx = \hbar/p$. Given that $V(x)$, one does not have to worry about $dt = \hbar/E$ because a conservation of energy equation, based on the classical:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((14))$$

does not include time at all. Given $\exp(ipx)$, ((14)) becomes the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there are two ways to describe the interaction of a free particle with a force system (e.g. 2 slit system). The first way is to consider $dp/dt = F$ (Newton's second law) and argue that if $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$ for a conservative force, p , which is like a force, should be describable as $\text{grad } \text{partial } G(x, t)$ and we set $G(x, t) = -Et + px$ in Part 1 to make it Lorentz invariant. We note that in special relativity a rest mass m_0 has inertia and so is like a force, because it requires a force to move it (i.e. Newton's action reaction). E and p are obtained by Lorentz boosting $m_0 c c$, and so both must be linked to the notion of interaction or force, we argue. We suggest that $-Et + px$ represents the potential, created by a free particle. Now for a

given x , t (perhaps $x=vt$), there is a second $x+h\bar{p}$, $t+h\bar{E}$ which yields the same potential value. We suggest that this means that the potential created by the free particle is stochastic and there may be interactions at different dt or dx . This becomes important if an interaction is with a 2-slit apparatus. In such a case, one is not really interested in dt , but dx is crucial if the slits are about $h\bar{p}$ apart. We suggest that one may describe free particle interactions using the probability $\exp(ipx)$.

There is a second way in which to describe interactions and that is Lagrangian theory, which is consistent with Newtonian mechanics. This theory should somehow be linked to the single particle potential theory given above because one cannot have two independent theories describing the same thing. One may argue that $dx=h\bar{p}$ and $dt=h\bar{E}$ do not appear in Lagrangian theory, but if these are small compared to dx , dt tiny units in a system, one no longer has a stochastic theory and the Lagrange theory should be exact.

We suggest here that one may see the link between Lagrangian theory and the single particle potential theory clearly because the classical action $L \cdot t$ is $-Et+px$ if one uses $v=x/t$ for a free particle. We note that the formal definition of v is dx/dt , but this forces $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$, while the single particle potential theory does not make this claim. Thus, using $v=x/t$ for a free particle (starting point $x=0$, $t=0$), one makes the two theories compatible for a free particle.

The problem is then the case in which there is a potential $V(x)$. Lagrangian theory uses $v=dx/dt$ explicitly when solving $D \int dt L(x, dx/dt, t) = 0$. This implies that an interaction with $V(x)$ must occur in a $dx \rightarrow 0$, but the single particle potential theory shows that this is not the case if $dx=h\bar{p}$ is not tiny compared with the system length. Thus, $v=dx/dt$ as describing an interaction with $V(x)$ breaks down in the traditional Lagrangian formalism if $dx=h\bar{p}$ is not tiny or at least of the order of dx (tiny on a system scale). As a result, in such cases, the single particle potential theory $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ properly describes interactions with $V(x)$ in terms of various single particle p potentials. One may use the classical conservation of energy equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ and write: $\{-1/2m d/dx d/dx W\} / W + V(x) = E$ and using $W(x) \rightarrow 0$ at \pm infinite obtain the Schrodinger equation and discrete E_n values.

The point of this note is to show that link between the single particle potential theory and Lagrangian formalism.